

Faculty of Sport and Physical Education

University of Novi Sad

4th International Scientific Conference

EXERCISE AND QUALITY OF LIFE

April 22nd / 23rd, 2016

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Novi Sad, 2016

Publisher: Faculty of Sport and Physical Education, University of Novi Sad
21000 Novi Sad, Lovćenska 16, Serbia

Editor-in-Chief: Dejan Madić, PhD

Executive Editor: Višnja Đorđić, PhD

Technical Editor: Damjan Jakšić, MSc

Printed by: SZR "Grafoana", Novi Sad, Serbia

Printed in: 500 copies.

CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотека Матице српске, Нови Сад

796.03:613.9(082)(048)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference Exercise and Quality of Life (4 ; 2016 ; Novi Sad)

Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / 4th International Scientific Conference Exercise and Quality of Life, Novi Sad, April 22nd/23rd 2016 ; editor-in-chief Dejan Madić. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Sport and Physical Education, 2016. - 1 elektronski optički disk (CD-ROM) ; 12 cm

ISBN 978-86-6353-019-5

а) Физичка активност - Квалитет живота - Зборници - Апстракти
COBISS.SR-ID [305070087](#)

ISBN: 978-86-6353-019-5

4th International Scientific Conference
EXERCISE AND QUALITY OF LIFE
April 22nd / 23rd, 2016

ADVISORY BOARD

1. Vladimir Koprivica –Belgrade, Serbia
2. Stevo Popović – Nikšić, Montenegro
3. Snežana Brkić – Novi Sad, Serbia
4. Nusret Smajlovic – Sarajevo, Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina
5. Simo Vuković – Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska
6. Đurđica Miletić – Split, Croatia
7. Damir Knjaz – Zagreb, Croatia
8. Milovan Bratić – Niš, Serbia
9. Milan Žvan – Ljubljana, Slovenia
10. Vujica Živković – Skoplje, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
11. Boštjan Šinunič – Koper, Slovenia
12. Boris Maleš – Split, Croatia
13. Duško Bjelica – Nikšić, Montenegro

SCIENTIFIC BOARD

Chair: Dejan Madić

Secretaries General: Višnja Đorđić, Marko Stojanović

Members:

1. Daniela Caporossi – Rome, Italy
2. Sandra Mandić – Dunedin, New Zealand
3. Tuija Tammelin – Jyvaskyla, Finland
4. Roger Harris – Chichester, UK
5. Rado Pišot –Koper, Slovenia
6. Goran Sporiš – Zagreb, Croatia
7. Adrian Nagel –Timisoara, Romania
8. Ioan Galea –Arad, Romania
9. Branko Krsmanović – Novi Sad, Serbia
10. Dragoslav Jakonić– Novi Sad, Serbia
11. Milena Mikalački – Novi Sad, Serbia
12. Ilona Mihajlović – Novi Sad, Serbia
13. Milorad Đukić – Novi Sad, Serbia
14. Nebojša Maksimović – Novi Sad, Serbia
15. Tatjana Tubić – Novi Sad, Serbia
16. Slavko Molnar – Novi Sad, Serbia
17. Borislav Obradović – Novi Sad, Serbia
18. Zoran Milošević – Novi Sad, Serbia
19. Sergej Ostojić – Novi Sad, Serbia
20. Patrik Drid – Novi Sad, Serbia
21. Milan Cvetković – Novi Sad, Serbia
22. Miroslav Smajić – Novi Sad, Serbia
23. Branka Protić-Gava – Novi Sad, Serbia
24. Mira Milić – Novi Sad, Serbia
25. Boris Popović – Novi Sad, Serbia
26. Nebojša Čokorilo – Novi Sad, Serbia
27. Željko Krneta – Novi Sad, Serbia
28. Goran Dimitrić – Novi Sad, Serbia
29. Goran Vasić – Novi Sad, Serbia
30. Maja Batez – Novi Sad, Serbia
31. Ivana Milovanović – Novi Sad, Serbia

THE EFFECT OF FUNCTIONAL TRAINING ON DYNAMOMETRIC, ANTHROPOMETRIC AND MOTOR CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUNG NON-ATHLETES

Miodrag Drapšin, Enis Garipi, Maja Bogdan, Dea Karaba-Jakovljević, & Vedrana Karan

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract

The concept of functional training emerged in medical rehabilitation and its application is found in sports. It is based on the use of specific exercises for specific sports discipline. Functional training increases mobility and joint stability, strength, speed and motor coordination through neural remodeling. The purpose of the research was to determine the influence of functional training on dynamometric, anthropometric and motor characteristics of young non-athletes. The analysis included 30 healthy people, 15 men and 15 women from the University of Novi Sad, who were not physically active 6 months before the start of the experiment. All subjects had undergone dynamometric, anthropometric tests and motor abilities before and after the completion of the eight-week of functional training. The use of the Student's t-test showed that there was a statistically significant improvement in motor characteristics after the completion of functional training ($p = 0.00$, $p < 0.01$; $p = 0.037$, $p < 0.05$). A significant statistical difference in the dynamometric parameters before and after training was observed at the level of $p < 0.01$, which means that the training resulted in significant improvement of all relevant parameters. The results of anthropometric measurements, expressed BF (%) index, showed that the percentage of body fat significantly decreased after the completion of functional training ($p = 0.008$, $p < 0.01$). Functional training has a significant positive impact on the explosive strength and muscular endurance, and also leads to a reduction of body fat.

Keywords: functional training, strength, body composition.